

AQUARIUS Brokerage Event

Marine Institute

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About this document

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1. Summary

Deliverable D1.2 details the AQUARIUS brokerage events (AQUARIUS Task 1.3) designed to introduce the AQUARIUS Transnational Access Portfolio to the Marine and Freshwater Research Community prior to the first Transnational Access call launch.

It includes three significant in-person events held at major conferences, one online webinar, and several smaller working group meetings and presentations and outreach activities. This document outlines the different brokerage events, the strategies employed, and their impact and reach within the Marine and Freshwater Research Community. It details how the events were organized, the key activities conducted, and the effectiveness in raising awareness of the AQUARIUS Transnational Access Portfolio.

2. Introduction & Objectives

As stated in the AQUARIUS Description of Action, the primary objective of the brokerage events was to launch the AQUARIUS Transnational Access Portfolio to the Marine and Freshwater Research Community.

This initiative aimed to raise awareness of access to integrated infrastructures through presentations from each project area and subsequent networking sessions for researchers. Smaller brokerage events were organized alongside larger conferences to ensure a significant audience. The project coordination team, work package leaders, and infrastructure operators were present, offering a general overview of the AQUARIUS project, details on Transnational Access Call themes, eligibility criteria, evaluation processes, training opportunities, and data management approaches. Infrastructure operators also showcased posters and engaged in networking activities.

3. Approach

For Task 1.3, team members decided that instead of a single large brokerage event, to which people would have to travel to attend at their own cost, multiple smaller events would be held alongside major conferences to reach a wider audience and ensure a regional balance.

These events would focus on the Mission Ocean Lighthouse regions: Atlantic/Arctic, Mediterranean, North Sea/Baltic, and Black Sea/Danube.

The Marine Institute, leading this task, worked with Consortium members to identify relevant conferences. The events were timed between September and early November 2024 to ensure they occurred after key deliverables (D3.1 Call Priority and D3.3 Design and Definition of Transnational Access Calls) were completed and the online Infrastructures Catalogue was available, but before the first Call Opening on November 11, 2024. The main brokerage events are as listed.

1. ICES Annual Science Conference, Newcastle, UK - 9th September 2024
2. MonGOOS General Assembly and Workshop, Malaga, Spain - 1st October 2024
3. Marblue Conference, Constanta, Romania - 23rd - 25th October 2024
4. Brokerage Event Webinar - 6th November 2024, Online

4. Brokerage Event No.1 - ICES Annual Science Conference

The first AQUARIUS project brokerage event was held at the annual International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) science conference on September 10th in Gateshead, United Kingdom. ICES is an intergovernmental marine science organization. It is composed of over 6000 experts, 700 institutes and organizations, 150 expert groups and contributors from over 60 countries.

The event convened leading experts, researchers, and industry professionals to delve into the opportunities in marine and freshwater research that the AQUARIUS project presents.

The AQUARIUS brokerage event took place in the Northern Rock room of the Glasshouse Exhibition Centre, as a side-event during the ICES Annual Science Conference between 6.00 PM and 7.30 PM on September 10th, 2024. The event was coordinated and attended by the AQUARIUS project team.

The event was designed with a focus on both operators and scientists, in total there was 49 attendees from across the marine and freshwater cohorts.

Event registration was managed via Eventbrite which had over 539 page visits.

LinkedIn and X(Twitter) were the chosen platforms used to promote and highlight the event. On LinkedIn 6 posts in total advertised the brokerage event with a combined total of 3,560 impressions. Similarly, X had 4 posts advertising the brokerage event with a combined total of 1,327 views. A news item on the AQUARIUS website included additional information, the agenda and registration link. All partners were encouraged to promote the brokerage event. The event was extensively promoted throughout the ICES conference with over 200 flyers circulated to attendees via the AQUARIUS project team.

The format of the event composed of four presentations. Aodhán Fitzgerald, AQUARIUS Project Coordinator overviewed the AQUARIUS project, its format, design and its Transnational Access funding calls. Anneli Strobel of the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) overviewed the AQUARIUS calls for proposals, call design and application platform. AQUARIUS training opportunities were overviewed by Andrea Caburlotto, of The National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics (OGS). In closing AQUARIUS data management and open science practices were overviewed by Dick M.A Schaap, MARIS.

Figure 1. AQUARIUS Project Team Attending 1st Brokerage Event at ICES

Figure 2. - AQUARIUS Poster Session at ICES

Applicants were advised to begin building their proposals as soon as the call opens, and to explore the online infrastructure catalogue in advance, to ensure that their proposals reflect an understanding of available resources. They were encouraged to visit the AQUARIUS website, stay tuned to social media channels and sign up to the newsletter to join the AQUARIUS community and be kept informed of updates and activities.

Upon completion of the presentations, networking, question and answer and discussion times were provided for.

Posters were presented at the event overviewing over 42 of the 56 AQUARIUS infrastructure. Eight operators were on site to present their posters and facilitate questions. The AQUARIUS infrastructure catalogue was widely promoted via a rolling slide show on multiple event screens. This session saw participants actively engaging with the AQUARIUS team and exploring the posters showcasing the various research infrastructures available through AQUARIUS.

AQUARIUS [brochures](#), QR coded stickers, pins and project branded pens were widely distributed amongst attendees.

Figure 3. - AQUARIUS Project Coordinator Aodhán Fitzgerald at the 1st AQUARIUS Brokerage Event

Questions from participants were noted and shared in the [FAQ page](#) on the AQUARIUS website.

Examples of Promotional Materials - Brokerage Event No.1

By Maria Angel Hinestroza • 7/26/2024

AQUARIUS-RI
495 followers
1mo • Edited •

🌟 Register Now!
Are you attending the **International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) Annual Science Conference**? Join us for the first AQUARIUS Brokerage Event where we will launch our upcoming Transnational Access funding calls!

📅 Tuesday, September 10th
🕒 18:00 - 19:30
📍 Gateshead, UK
🔗 Link for registration https://lnkd.in/evQkZ_7V
👉 For more information visit our website: <https://lnkd.in/e46myauw>

🔴 First Transnational Access Funding Call Open: 11 November 2024 - 20 January 2025

Don't miss this chance to learn about:

- ✓ The AQUARIUS Research Infrastructures Portfolio
- ✓ Upcoming Transnational Access Funding Calls
- ✓ Training Opportunities
- ✓ FAIR Data Management

Meet our research infrastructures operators and enjoy networking opportunities with refreshments 🍷 🍷 🍷

📌 Agenda

6:00 PM – 6:05 PM
Introduction to the AQUARIUS Project and available Infrastructure
Aodhán Fitzgerald (MI)

6:05 PM – 6:20 PM
The AQUARIUS Calls for Proposals – Call Design & Application Platform
Anneli Strobel (AWI)

6:20 PM – 6:25 PM
AQUARIUS Training Opportunities
Andrea Caburlotto

6:25 PM – 6:30 PM
AQUARIUS Data Management
Dick Schaap (MARIS)

6:30 PM – 7:30 PM
Meet the Research Infrastructure Providers and Networking!

Figure 4. - 1st AQUARIUS Brokerage Event LinkedIn Post

ICES 2024 Annual Science Conference
9-12 September, Gateshead, UK

1st AQUARIUS Brokerage Event

10 SEPTEMBER 2024

Side Event to the ICES ASC

AQUARIUS

Figure 6. - 1st AQUARIUS Brokerage Event LinkedIn Post

Figure 5. - AQUARIUS Project Promotional Pin

ICES 2024 Annual Science Conference
9-12 September, Gateshead, UK

AQUARIUS

1st AQUARIUS Brokerage Event

10 SEPTEMBER 2024 - 6pm

Join us in the Northern Rock Room,
Tuesday 10th September @6pm for the AQUARIUS
Brokerage Event where we will launch the upcoming
Transnational Access funding calls.

Visit aquarius-ri.eu

Funded by the European Union

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Figure 7. - 1st AQUARIUS Brokerage Event Promotional Flyer

5. Brokerage Event No. 2 - MonGOOS Annual Workshop and General Assembly

The second AQUARIUS project brokerage event was held at the annual Mediterranean Operational Network for the Global Ocean Observing System (MonGOOS) workshop and General Assembly meeting on October 1st, 2024, in Malaga, Spain. This event was hosted by Instituto Español De Oceanografía.

MonGOOS was established in 2012 to further develop operational oceanography in the Mediterranean Sea. MonGoos is a regional partner of the GOOS alliance focused on developing and promoting the operational oceanographic services in the Mediterranean. The event assembled 50 MonGOOS members from across the Mediterranean.

AQUARIUS had a standalone agenda time slot which was specifically designed around AQUARIUS research infrastructures in the Mediterranean, which were highlighted during the assembly. AQUARIUS project team members provided a presentation with an overview of the project, training opportunities, its data management and open science approach and its Transnational Access Funding Calls.

The assembly further underscored the strategic significance of the project for fostering accessibility to research facilities and technology across Europe. This presentation was live streamed by Instituto Español De Oceanografía on YouTube.

The assembly also saw the introduction of the forthcoming "Regional Lighthouse Access Call", aimed at supporting projects addressing scientific challenges aligned to the Mission Ocean and Waters in the Mission Lighthouse regions: the Baltic, North Sea, Black Sea, Atlantic/Arctic, Mediterranean, and their connected river basins. The announcement generated significant interest from participants and the team invited scientists to submit proposals.

Applicants were again advised to begin building their proposals as soon as the call opens, and to explore the infrastructure catalogue in advance, to ensure that their proposals reflect an understanding of available resources and to follow the website and social media accounts for updates.

Figure 8. - AQUARIUS Project Team and Poster Session at the MonGOOS Workshop and General Assembly

LinkedIn and X(Twitter) were the chosen platforms used to promote and highlight the event. On LinkedIn, 2 posts in total advertised the brokerage event with a combined total of 941 impressions.

Similarly, X had 1 post advertising the brokerage event with a combined total of 464 impressions. The event was extensively promoted throughout the MonGOOS website, event agenda and promotional materials.

A standalone poster session was also facilitated where 18 posters were presented all highlighting Mediterranean infrastructure available via AQUARIUS. Seven operators were in attendance to overview their infrastructure available. The project team also shared the AQUARIUS infrastructure catalogue on large screens where again specific infrastructure was overviewed garnering interest among the attendees. All event attendees participated in this poster session where significant time was provided for questions, discussions and networking.

AQUARIUS brochures, QR coded stickers, pins and project branded pens were widely distributed and shared amongst attendees. Questions from participants were noted and shared in the [FAQ page](#) on the AQUARIUS website.

Examples of Promotional Materials - Brokerage Event No.2

General Assembly Agenda
Malaga - Spain
 Hosted by the Instituto Español de Oceanografía

Tuesday 01 October

8:30-9:30 Registration

Morning Session

09:00 - 11:00 Session

09.20 - 09.40 Welcome by the host institution General Director (CSIC -IEO) and Director of the Malaga Center

09.40 - 09.50 Welcome by MonGOOS chair

09.50 - 10.20 Invited Lecture "Field Notes from a Catastrophe: A journey through the Mediterranean Sea" - E. Azzurro (CNR-IRBIM)

10.20 - 10.40 MonGOOS update and involvement in the Decade - V. Cardin (Chair - OGS)

10.40 - 11.00 Outcomes of MonGOOS Modeling WG within OceanPrediction DCC* - E. Clementi (CMCC)

11:00-11:30 coffee break/ Aquarius Poster Session

11:30-13:00 Session

11.30 - 11.45 MonGOOS Application Group: progress and challenges - S. Liubartseva (CMCC)/ K. Spanoudaki (FORTH-TUC)

11.45 - 12.00 Updating our knowledge about observing capabilities in the Mediterranean Sea - Manolo Vargas (CSIC - IEO) - O. de Fommervault (OceanOPS)

12.00 - 12.15 Monaco Exploration - O. de Fommervault

12.15 - 13.00 AQUARIUS Project Upcoming Transnational Access Funding Calls.

The AQUARIUS project is a Horizon Europe funded project providing Transnational Access to a comprehensive and diverse suite of integrated Marine and Freshwater research infrastructures. The AQUARIUS team will introduce the Research Infrastructures portfolio, upcoming Transnational Access Funding Calls opening in November 2024, training opportunities and the AQUARIUS FAIR Data Management approach. There will also be networking opportunities with the coordination team and AQUARIUS infrastructure operators.

13:00-14:30 Lunch/ Aquarius Poster Session

Figure 9. - AQUARIUS Brokerage Event No.2 - MonGOOS Agenda

Climate change

United Nations - Climate change refers to long-term shifts in temperatures and weather patterns. Human activities have been the main driver of climate change, primarily due to the burning of fossil fuels like coal, oil and gas.

MonGOOS

Instituto Español de Oceanografía 1.29K subscribers

153 views Streamed live on Oct 1, 2024
 Spanish Institute of Oceanography. Málaga Oceanographic Center. MonGOOS annual General assembly and workshop. 1 to 3 October 2024.

Figure 11. & 12. - AQUARIUS Brokerage Event No.2 Project Team Presentation Live Streamed Via YouTube

ISC-Lab ISMAR Calibration Laboratory

Fixed Marine Facility

Manufacturing and installation of the ISMAR calibration system for the Aquarius project.

Climate change

United Nations - Climate change refers to long-term shifts in temperatures and weather patterns. Human activities have been the main driver of climate change, primarily due to the burning of fossil fuels like coal, oil and gas.

MonGOOS

Instituto Español de Oceanografía 1.29K subscribers

Figure 10. - AQUARIUS Promotional Sticker

6. Brokerage Event No. 3 – MARBLUE 2nd International Joint Conference

The third AQUARIUS project brokerage event took place on the 22nd and 23rd of October 2024 as part of the MARBLUE 2nd International Joint Conference and was held at the “Ovidius” University of Constanta, Romania. The event was hosted by AQUARIUS partner GeoEcoMar, in collaboration with Ovidius University, the National Institute for Marine Research and Development (INCDM) and Mare Nostrum, an environmental NGO based in Constanta.

This was the second iteration of the MARBLUE conference, the first having been held in 2022, with plans to continue it on a biennial basis. The conference aims to protect the Black Sea by promoting sustainable development through a multidisciplinary approach. It is designed to foster productive discussions on fundamental research and technological innovations among scientists and industry experts in research and development. This year the event was attended by approximately 100 individuals from scientific, academic and industry backgrounds.

Both a presentation and poster were submitted for the conference to promote AQUARIUS. Bernadette Ní Chonghaile presented a 15-minute talk about the project during the first morning session, which was themed: “Observing the Black Sea”, providing an overview of the project, its training opportunities, data management approach and its Transnational Access Funding Calls. It also specifically highlighted the infrastructures and services that would be made available within the Danube and Black Sea Lighthouse region. Frank Armstrong also presented a poster on the second day of the conference during an allocated poster session.

The conference also saw a presentation from an AQUARIUS partner from SOCIB, Nikolaos D. Zarokanellos, who demonstrated how their ocean gliders were used to reveal restratification processes and resultant biogeochemical impact in the Black Sea, and in addition, enhance our observing capabilities and contribute to the regional Digital Twins.

Figure 13. & 14. – AQUARIUS Project Coordinator and Project Officer in attendance at the MARBLUE 2nd International Joint Conference

Figure 15. & 16. – AQUARIUS Project Table at MARBLUE 2nd International Joint Conference / AQUARIUS Brokerage Event No.3

The AQUARIUS data management and open science practices were presented by Claudia Coman (MARIS). In total three AQUARIUS abstracts appeared in the conference [Book of Abstracts](#). In addition, a project table was arranged at the conference to promote the project during lunch and coffee breaks. This was used as an opportunity to disseminate promotional material and to further engage with attendees. Day 2 of the conference saw quite a lot of interest in the AQUARIUS project from several Black Sea based researchers enquiring about the availability of infrastructure to carry out scientific research in the region.

AQUARIUS’s presence at the event was highlighted using social media platforms, which had 2 posts on X (Twitter) and 1 post on LinkedIn. The 2 posts on X (Twitter) had a combined number of 499 views while the LinkedIn post had 19 likes and 2 reposts.

Questions from participants were noted and shared in the [FAQ page](#) on the project website.

Examples of Promotional Materials - Brokerage Event No.3

Wednesday, 23 October 2024 - Amphitheatre A3	
09:00 – 09:30	Registration
09:30 – 10:30	Prof. Dr. Adrian Stănică Director General GeoEcoMar
	Prof. Dr. Ing. Tudor Prisecaru Secretary of State, Romanian Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization
	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Alexandru Avram General Secretary, Romanian Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests
	Ms. Elisabetta Balzi Head of Unit, DG RTD
	Ms. Andreea Strachinescu Head of Unit, DG MARE
	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Dan Marcel Iliescu Rector of the Ovidius University of Constanta
	Dr. Florin Timofte General Director NIMRD
Assoc. Prof. Dr. Marius Radu Dean of the Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Sciences, Ovidius University of Constanta	
Mr. Marian Paiu Executive Director Mare Nostrum NGO	
10:30 – 10:50	Coffee break
Session I: Observing the Black Sea - Moderator GeoEcoMar	
Chairpersons: Andrew Tyler, Adrian Stănică	
Invited Speaker Violeta Slabakova - IO-BAS, Varna, Bulgaria	
	Authors/Co-authors (*presenter is underlined)
	Title of the abstract
11:20 – 11:35	Dina Eparkhina, <u>Alberto Basset</u> , Yann-Herve De Roeck, Natalia Fedoronchuk, Aljaz Maslo, Kalliopi Pagou, Mery Pina, Adrian Stanica
	ECOSYSTEM RESPONSES TO CLIMATE CHANGE
11:35 – 11:50	Nikolaos D. Zarokanellos, Manuel Rubio, Sorin Balan, Viorel Gh. Ungureanu, Albert Miralles, Sabin Rotaru, Patricia Rivera Rodríguez, Vangelis Papatthanassiou, Andrew Tyler, Benjamin Casas, Adrian Stanica, Joaquin Tintore
	REVEALING RESTRATIFICATION PROCESSES AND THEIR BIOGEOCHEMICAL IMPACT IN THE BLACK SEA: INSIGHTS FROM UNDERWATER GLIDER OBSERVATIONS
11:50 – 12:05	<u>Elizabeth C. Atwood</u> , Bror F. Jönsson, Evangelos Spyros, Dalin Jiang, Violeta Slabakova, Andrew N. Tyler
	DOMINANT TIMESCALES OF OPTICAL VARIABILITY IN SURFACE BLACK SEA WATERS
12:05 – 12:20	<u>Yann-Herve De Roeck</u> , Violeta Slabakova, Atanas Palazov
	IN-DEPTH CHARACTERIZATION OF THE BLACK SEA WITH A SUSTAINED ARGO FLEET
12:20 – 12:35	<u>Bernadette Ni Chonghaile</u> , Frank Armstrong
	AQUARIUS - INTEGRATING RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURES - CONNECTING SCIENTISTS - ENABLING TRANSNATIONAL ACCESS FOR HEALTHY AND SUSTAINABLE MARINE AND FRESHWATER ECOSYSTEMS
12:35 – 12:50	<u>Jean-François Grailet</u> , Xavier Fettweis, Marilaure Grégoire
	SIMULATING THE ATMOSPHERE ABOVE THE BLACK SEA WITH THE MAR (V3.14) REGIONAL MODEL: FUTURE PROJECTIONS AND PERSPECTIVES
12:50 – 13:00	<u>Dimitar Trukhchev</u> , <u>Ekaterina Bachvarova</u> , Anton Krastev, Radka Mavrodieva, Valentin Georgiev
	SPATIAL-TEMPORAL VARIABILITY OF BASIC HYDROLOGICAL, HYDROCHEMICAL, HYDROBIOLOGICAL AND METEOROLOGICAL PARAMETERS OF THE VARNA LAKES DURING THE PERIOD 2022-2023
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch break

Figure 17. - AQUARIUS Brokerage Event No.3 - MARBLUE 2nd International Joint Conference - AQUARIUS Agenda

Figure 19. - AQUARIUS Brokerage Event No.3 LinkedIn Post

Figure 18. - MARBLUE 2nd International Joint Conference - Group Photo

7. AQUARIUS Brokerage Webinar

The AQUARIUS Brokerage Webinar took place on November 6th, 2024 at 10:00 AM GMT.

The webinar was focused on gathering potential applicants who were unable to travel or attend other brokerage events previously located throughout Europe or applicants who wished to gather additional AQUARIUS knowledge. It also provided an opportunity to record the event and make it available via the AQUARIUS website.

The webinar was designed with a spotlight on sharing and disseminating information in relation to overall project approach, call design, training opportunities and data management and open science practices.

Aodhán Fitzgerald, AQUARIUS Project Coordinator overviewed the AQUARIUS project, its format, design and its Transnational Access funding calls. Anneli Strobel of the Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI) overviewed the AQUARIUS calls for proposals, call design and application platform. AQUARIUS training opportunities were overviewed by Andrea Caburlotto, of The National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics (OGS). In closing AQUARIUS data management and open science practices were overviewed by Peter Thijsse of MARIS.

The webinar was extensively advertised via LinkedIn and X (Twitter). Zoom was the chosen platform for webinar presentation. Applicants were encouraged via LinkedIn and X (Twitter) to register in advance.

Almost 100 participants joined live online, with over 160 participants registered from 24 countries.

Question time and discussion was facilitated with 15 participants engaging with questions to presenters.

The webinar was recorded and shared on [YouTube](#) and all AQUARIUS communication platforms.

Figure 20. - AQUARIUS Brokerage Webinar LinkedIn Post

8. Other Outreach Events

8.1 ERVO 2024

Marine Institute colleagues participated in the European Research Vessel Operators (ERVO) meeting, held in Vigo, Spain, on June 11, 2024.

ERVO meetings bring together research vessel operators from across Europe to discuss shared challenges and issues, with the goal of finding solutions that enhance services provided to the scientific community and promote the development of best practices for operating research vessels.

At this meeting, Rosemarie Butler from the Marine Institute delivered a presentation on the AQUARIUS project, providing an insightful overview to the audience. Her presentation was particularly relevant to attendees, some of whom already have infrastructure available through the AQUARIUS project, while others may be interested in exploring potential collaborations with existing infrastructure providers. This exchange fostered discussions about collaboration opportunities and improving research capabilities within the community.

Figure 21. & 22. AQUARIUS Project Representation at ERVO 2024

8.2 Oceanology International

In February 2024, AQUARIUS project coordinator Aodhán Fitzgerald and project officer Frank Armstrong (MI) attended Oceanology International (OI) in London as part of a larger team from the Marine Institute.

OI is a major global event centered on ocean science, marine technology, and the industries associated with ocean exploration and preservation, bringing together marine professionals from various sectors.

Figure 23. AQUARIUS Project Coordinator and Project Officer in attendance at Oceanology International

This event was used as a platform to promote and highlight the diverse transnational, remote and virtual access that would be made available as part of AQUARIUS to scientific communities and the industry sector. The OI conference proved to be an ideal venue for this outreach effort.

The team engaged with a wide range of scientists from various disciplines, including marine biology, oceanography, environmental science, and maritime engineering, allowing them to discuss potential applications for AQUARIUS across different projects.

Overall, the event was a successful networking and promotional opportunity, strengthening relationships with the scientific community and laying the groundwork for future collaborations.

8.3 12th Ferrybox Workshop

The 12th Ferrybox Workshop, jointly coordinated by AQUARIUS partners the Finnish Environment Institute (SYKE) and the Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI), was held in Helsinki from October 1–2, 2024.

The Ferrybox Workshop series is a long-running event that brings together marine scientists, researchers, and technology experts who use or manage Ferrybox systems. These systems are crucial for monitoring physical, chemical, and biological properties of the sea, offering real-time data on factors such as temperature, salinity, chlorophyll levels, and nutrient concentrations.

Attended by over 70 experts from the scientific community, the workshop provided a valuable platform to showcase AQUARIUS and its opportunities for transnational access to advanced marine research infrastructure, including Ferryboxes.

AQUARIUS representatives Jukka Seppälä (SYKE), Lauri Laakso (FMI), Andrew Luke King (NIVA), and Yoana Voynova (Hereon), all of whom manage or operate Ferryboxes systems available through AQUARIUS, participated in the event. They presented posters highlighting the AQUARIUS Ferrybox infrastructure, along with other resources offered by SYKE and FMI. This facilitated productive discussions on potential applications for upcoming calls.

Figure 24. AQUARIUS Project Representation at the 12th Ferrybox Workshop

8.4 EMRA 2024

Simo Cusi, Engineer and Logistics Officer at the European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory (EMSO) of the European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC), presented AQUARIUS in a workshop on EU-funded Marine Robotics and Applications (EMRA'24), organized by the Italian National Research Council (INM-CNR). AQUARIUS infographics were also disseminated to attendees.

Figure 25. Simo Cusi Introduced AQUARIUS at EMRA

The two-day workshop took place in Arezano, Italy on 28-29 May 2024. EMRA is a meeting point for marine robotics engineers but also for different stakeholders interested in automated ways to monitor the ocean. This was a great opportunity to highlight AQUARIUS to a more applied audience, including to industry.

8.5 Sea Basin Strategies Days

AQUARIUS colleagues, Oonagh McMeel and Maria Angel (Seascope Belgium), participated in the 5th EU Macro-Regional Sea Basin Strategy Days Conference held in Brussels on 12 and 13 June 2024, co-organised by the Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy (DG REGIO) and the Directorate-General for Maritime Affairs and Fisheries (DG MARE).

This event was an opportunity to connect with stakeholders across the regions encompassed by the seven

Figure 26. AQUARIUS Project Information at Sea Basin Strategies Day

strategies (Alpine, Danube, Adriatic-Ionian, Baltic Sea, Atlantic, Western Mediterranean and Black Sea) and disseminate the AQUARIUS infographic.

There was an opportunity in the 'Clusters and Innovation' workshop to introduce AQUARIUS and share the AQUARIUS infographic, highlighting the regional spread of AQUARIUS research infrastructures and the upcoming Calls for Transnational Access. The conference also underscored European support for Ukraine, showcasing tangible forms of assistance amidst ongoing challenges and provided an opportunity to make contacts in this region. Contacts were encouraged to sign up to the AQUARIUS newsletter and follow the social media channels and website for updates on the TA calls.

Examples of Promotional Materials - Other Outreach Events

Figure 27. AQUARIUS Project Promotional Brochure

Figure 28 and 29. AQUARIUS Project Promotional Materials - Pens, Lanyards, Chocolates and Pens

9.0 In Conclusion

The AQUARIUS brokerage events were highly successful, effectively promoting the AQUARIUS Transnational Access (TA) Portfolio, TA calls, training opportunities, and data management approach to a broad audience, including early career scientists, women scientists and vulnerable groups. With approximately 360 attendees participating directly and hundreds more reached through social media, flyers, and the website, including having direct access to the Webinar recording, the outreach exceeded expectations. Ongoing engagement and project membership was encouraged via the AQUARIUS website, social media channels and subscribing to the project newsletter to join the AQUARIUS community and be kept informed of updates and activities.

The events met and surpassed the target of engaging over 500 stakeholders, as outlined in the AQUARIUS description of action, achieving significant visibility and engagement ahead of the first TA call opening. Notably, this figure excludes additional outreach efforts made by the 45 consortium members, who also actively promoted the brokerage events and TA Call among their extensive contacts' lists.

Monthly WP7 (Dissemination and Communication) meetings are held to identify outreach opportunities for partners to further promote AQUARIUS and provide partners with communication and outreach materials and support. Dedicated communication toolkits have been developed for the launch of the research infrastructure catalogue and for the first TA call. The latter included pre and post launch communication and outreach materials including template social media and email posts, flyer, videos for social media, website banners and a press release.

Following the final AQUARIUS brokerage webinar, AQUARIUS LinkedIn followers had grown to 600, with noted increases around brokerage event dates as evident from Figure 30. There were over 110 subscribers to the AQUARIUS newsletter at that time and these figures continue to grow.

Figure 30. AQUARIUS Project LinkedIn Followers showing Peaks in New Followers around Brokerage Events